

THE RELEVANCE OF THE APPLICATION OF THE MIXED FORM OF EDUCATION IN HIGHER MILITARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Pazilova Sh. A.

Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Doctor of philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7534056>

Abstract. *This article will talk about the requirements imposed on the professional qualities of graduates of higher military educational institutions, about the importance of the educational form in which the knowledge gained plays an important role in the course of their professional activities and the involvement in the acquisition of such knowledge. The article also analyzes the achievements and disadvantages of the mixed learning method.*

Keywords: *mixed education, information technology, distance education, professional qualities, educational technologies, teaching educational process.*

INTRODUCTION

After humanity entered a new era, a new era of high technologies, artificial intelligence and digitalization, Society, Science, Science and education began to be informatized. The development of society is characterized by its characteristic features today. Such features can be attributed to the use of information resources at the global level, the need for information exchange, the integration of Science, Technology and education.

Informatization taking place in the world, like all spheres, affects the education system. As a result of the use of traditional and distance forms in education, the level of use of information technologies in the content of education, teaching methodology is changing. These created the need to use mixed forms of education in the learning process.

Great attention is paid to the fact that in our country, through the widespread introduction of modern knowledge and advanced foreign experience into the field of military education, it is important to raise the intellectual potential of future defenders of the motherland in the future development and its transformation into a great state, improve educational work, regularly explain them with the achievements of This justifies the need to create a modern teaching system that is flexible in the learning process and develop a mixed teaching system and content, taking into account the level of knowledge of cadets.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the requirements for the personal, intellectual, scientific and professional qualities of educators. This decision also indicates the support of innovative activities in educational organizations to ensure the right of an individual to education and the implementation of educational programs using innovative technologies. In our country, at present, the application of digital technologies to higher education is becoming widespread. The use of mixed educational technologies, which combines modern achievements of Science and technology to ensure that, while enriching the theoretical knowledge of students, they can apply their mastered knowledge in solving life-practical problems, expands the possibilities of

today's pedagogy. Mixed education is based on new didactic opportunities provided by electronic education, information and communication technologies and modern educational tools.

There are different opinions and views on mixed learning technologies. In his treatise entitled "The definition of mixed education", Norm Friesen determined that mixed education would be used from 1999 onwards. He also described mixed education as "a type of education that is offered by combining the Internet and electronic media with forms that require physical participation in the classroom between the teacher and the student." There are different opinions and views on mixed learning technologies. In his treatise entitled "The definition of mixed education", Norm Friesen determined that mixed education would be used from 1999 onwards. He also described mixed education as "a type of education that is offered by combining the Internet and electronic media with forms that require physical participation in the classroom between the teacher and the student."

The mixed education manual, published by Charles Graham and Bonk in 2006, describes mixed education as "computer-mediated learning is combined with face-to-face learning in mixed education systems."

As can be seen from the definitions of mixed education, mixed education is a learning strategy that combines traditional and distance learning and in which different forms of technology are applied.

RESULTS

Mixed learning is a combination of teaching methods that include elements of online and face-to-face learning. In this education, cadets can use teaching materials, video cards, textbooks and simulators. In order for the educational material to be preserved in the Information Resource Center, cadets have the opportunity to Re-study the topic. In addition to the lecture, a dialogue will be organized between the teacher–cadets and cadets. The materials for the lecture sessions are complete, and the presentation and slides should be enough for the cadets to engage independently. There are printed and electronic forms of textbooks and manuals on science, and the electronic form is interesting and convenient to master. Mixed education forms responsibilities and skills in working on the internet, analyzing information, working with a group, performing tasks. Hence, mixed education is an extremely flexible system that teaches cadets to organize their activities.

DISCUSSION

In a mixed educational method, various technologies and tools contribute to the inclusion of information in the educational material. The cadet can receive information from a book or from the internet at a convenient time for himself. To interest cadets, the data will consist of a clear structure. Each session will consist of several stages. At the initial stage, the cadet is prepared for the lesson, and this is done on the basis of an assignment. Then the lesson will be effective and there will be no excessive repetitions. At the present stage, the cadet has mastered the previous lesson well, and the lesson is strengthened by tests, questions and practical issues. At the next stage, the teacher first answers the questions of the cadet, and then comments on the tasks performed. At this stage, the cadet is guided by interest in the next topic. In each lesson, these stages are repeated, and the skills of cadets are formed, such as the ability to distinguish information, work independently, apply theoretical knowledge in practice.

The success of the mixed form of education depends on technical means. These tools should be reliable, easy to use and stylish so that they can be used efficiently. Mixed education has

several disadvantages. Cadets may not have the conditions to access the internet or study wherever he wants. Not every cadet may have access to computer and technical means. Unreliable Internet is also one of the problems.

CONCLUSION

When training in higher military educational institutions, of course, educational methods were used to take into account the educational institution, the specifics of cadets in it, while ensuring their active participation in training, aimed at cultivating, developing thinking.

It is necessary to form the world vision of the younger generation, to increase the educational importance of choosing a way of life. In terms of Science, the foundations of theory should be ensured by practice, the application of the issue with science, and with a creative approach to New pressing issues of the economy, the inextricable unity of theoretical facts with logic.

The current period is significant in that the forms of teaching are aimed at the excellent organization of the service of cadets to free, creative thinking. It is the basis of this teaching process when cadets can think independently, approach each issue creatively, search, analyze, draw the right conclusions. The main issue is how to apply the form of mixed education in higher military education, how to conduct part of the information to be provided online and which part to face. Through the use of mixed education, achievements such as improving the quality of education, developing independent educational skills in cadets, acting as a teacher-consultant can be achieved.

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on education (law national database of data, 24.09.2020., 03/20/637/1313-San).
2. Friesen N. Defining Blended Learning, August 2012, available at: https://www.normfresen.info/papers/Defining_Blended_LearningNF.pdf (request date: 21.06.2020)
3. Bonk, C.J. & Graham, C.R. (2006). The handbook of blended learning environments: Global perspectives, local designs. San Francisco: Jossey Bass/Pfeiffer. – 624 p.
4. Pazilova Sh. A. Improving the teaching of the discipline fundamentals of electrical engineering and electronics // Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2022, 1(6), 251 – 255.